

Eurodoc statement on the proposed options for MSCA-IF 2021-27

Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 28 national associations of early-career researchers (ECRs) from 26 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research and innovation in Europe.

Need for an increase in budget

In the [Eurodoc statement on FP9](#), we encouraged the European Commission (EC) to increase significantly the proposed budget by at least €50 billion to Pillar 1 for Excellent Science and for ECRs, especially due to the rising competition from the US and China. The budget for MSCA should be raised and the applications from ECRs should be encouraged by increasing the number of doctoral and postdoctoral positions and directing specific funding calls for ECRs.

Insufficient funding for ECRs at national level

The popularity and attractiveness of the MSCA-IF has been increasing annually due to good employment conditions it offers, for example, in terms of salary, training, mobility, and family allowance. Funding for ECRs at the national level needs not only to increase, but social benefits offered to those awarded with such funding need to be equalized with the social benefits offered by the MSCA-IF.

In many of the countries where Eurodoc is represented, ECRs often turn to the MSCA fellowships as a means of overcoming the shortage of publicly funded salaried positions at the national level. National governments need to devise mechanisms that adequately fund ECRs and facilitate the development of sustainable research careers.

“MSCA-IF” versus “MSCA Postdoc”

The central spirit of the [MSCA-IF](#) is to support mobility and excellent science and boost the career development of researchers. MSCA-IF fellows are acknowledged for their excellence and research potential. As such, the MSCA-IF helps the researchers move from a precarious contract ('postdoc') to a permanent position (e.g., as an assistant professor or full professor, as a full researcher integrated in a career, by being hired at a company, or by securing funding to start their own business activity). We believe that replacing the name “MSCA-IF” with “MSCA Postdoc” is a step back in this regard.

The term 'postdoc' is currently used to describe many of the roles and responsibilities of the R2¹ researchers. 'Postdoc' is a popular term to denominate researchers in their first years after their doctoral degree. However, it is most often used to refer to researchers on a fixed-term contract or fellowship, carrying the connotation of their precariousness. We, therefore, believe that a more precise terminology should be used to describe the position of the MSCA-IF fellows.

¹ According to the [European Framework for Research Careers](#), R2 researchers are defined as Recognised Researchers (PhD holders or equivalent who are not yet fully independent).

Eurodoc statement on the proposed options for MSCA-IF 2021-27

Namely, MSCA-IF fellows should be considered as principal investigators (PIs) rather than postdocs, as they should take on as much initiative and responsibility for the fellowship/action as possible. On the other hand, the supervisors, being the ones who (i) foster, mentor and support the fellow in his career, and (ii) have the final accountability at the hosting institution, should be recognized for their role as mentors rather than as supervisors.

1. Resubmission restrictions

We agree with the suggestion to include resubmission restrictions. To navigate the programs more easily, we suggest to align this further with the ERC restrictions for resubmissions, but without implementing a 2-step evaluation for the MSCA.

The conditions could thus be based on the quality of the submitted application as follows:

- Above a score of 85% (excellent), award the Seal of Excellence without the restrictions for the application in the following year/calls.
- Below a score of 85%, restrict the resubmission of the application in the following year (or in the next application if 2 calls per year are available).
- Below the threshold, that is a score of 70%, restrict the resubmission of the application in the following 2 years.

In addition, we propose a limitation of the number of applications, namely one successful MSCA-IF application per individual researcher.

2. Eligibility condition based on the qualification of the applicant:

Having a PhD as the entry criterion for applicants will not benefit this funding mechanism. It will create a career gap between the time of the fellow's thesis defense and the possible start of the grant. However, we agree that the MSCA-IF fellow should have been awarded the PhD at the moment of the signature of the grant agreement. We also propose that no more than eight months should pass between the announcement of the call results and the start of the action/fellowship. Exceptions need to be considered for those needing a visa.

3. Age restriction for IF

The main mission of the MSCA framework is to support mobility and excellent science for researchers at all career stages. Eurodoc thus does not support the proposal for a maximum number of years of experience in research after having obtained a PhD (or equivalent degree).

Therefore, Eurodoc proposes splitting the call into 2 categories:

- For researchers up to 7 years post-PhD, provide more funding and a possibility to extend the fellowship length from 2 to 3 years. The 3rd year might be reserved as a (re)integration period to the fellow's home country or another European country of choice, similar to the current situation with Global Fellowships;
- For researchers of more than 7 years post-PhD, provide 2 years of funding.

In this way, the mobility and cooperation would be maintained, awarding excellent research but giving some differentiation depending on the career stage. Further, the proposed

Eurodoc statement on the proposed options for MSCA-IF 2021-27

categories enable an emphasis on the career stage by distributing the volumes of allocated total funds.

Eurodoc agrees that breaks in the research career (e.g., parental leaves, sick leaves, military service, caring for seriously ill family members, medical specialty training) should not be taken into account when calculating the research experience, thus enabling the integration of all European fellowship sub-actions into a single one.

However, Eurodoc proposes that if a researcher is actively engaged in research activities outside Europe, that time should not count as a career break. These researchers should apply for the MSCA-IF under the same conditions as the researchers working in Europe.

Other suggestions

There could be more submission deadlines within one year - at least 2 instead of 1. This will help to disperse the workload of evaluators, who could then be divided into pools according to their availability in the given year.

We advocate for the researchers with a score of $\geq 85\%$ to be awarded the Seal of Excellence. We also appeal to the EC to further encourage national funding agencies to strengthen the synergy with national funding mechanisms by implementing complementary funding schemes for the ECRs who have been awarded the Seal of Excellence.

We suggest to increase the pool of experts registered to the EC to evaluate the applications. There are numerous excellent researchers in Europe that have the knowledge and skills to become evaluators and who can help to deal with the increasing number of applications. One alternative would be to further formalize the existing system to reward the evaluators (e.g., recognition on [Publons](#), [Open Science Framework](#)), and to increase awareness about the registration procedure for experts in the Funding & Tenders portal.

Concluding remarks

Eurodoc understands the preoccupation of the MSCA that leads to the desire to implement restrictions for those who are eligible to apply for the funding. However, the proposed restrictions, especially the ones pointing to a maximum number of years of research experience post-PhD (or equivalent degree), will not benefit the funding mechanism. In particular, they will not help to solve the key problem, which is the overall lack of adequate funding for ECRs. Such measures will only ensure a decrease in the number of applicants, artificially increasing the success rates and obscuring the true causes of the current surge in MSCA applicants.

Eurodoc believes it would be more efficient to either increase the budget for the MSCA or synergize the program with funding mechanisms offered at the national level.